

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12515728>

THE USE OF GAME TECHNOLOGY IN THE PROCESS OF FORMING THE CREATIVITY OF A STUDENT

Turaeva Nargiza Zokirjonovna

Namangan State University Teacher of the Department of methods of teaching exact
and Natural Sciences in primary education
turayevan880@gmail.com

Annotation. *In this article, the reforms carried out in the higher education system in our country, the problems of optimizing the educational process, the peculiarities of using Game Technology in the course of the lesson, the stages of identifying students' performance, as well as recommendations in this direction are given.*

Key words: *primary education, creativity, creative thinking, game technology, creative imagination, diagnostic stage, prognostic stage, problem situation.*

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИГРОВОЙ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ТВОРЧЕСКИХ СПОСОБНОСТЕЙ СПРОСА

Тураева Наргиза Закиржоновна

Преподаватель кафедры методики преподавания точных и естественных наук в
начальном образовании Наманганского государственного университета
turayevan880@gmail.com

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассмотрены проводимые в нашей стране реформы в системе высшего образования, проблемы оптимизации учебного процесса, особенности использования игровой технологии в процессе урока, этапы выявления творческих способностей учащихся и даны рекомендации в этом направлении.*

Ключевые слова: *начальное образование, творчество, творческое мышление, игровая технология, творческое воображение, диагностический этап, прогностический этап, проблемная ситуация.*

At the present stage of the development of the higher education system in our country, the main task is to improve the quality of professional training of graduates, ensuring their competitiveness in the labor market. For this, the problem of finding new approaches to the organization of the educational process, which contributes to the creative development of students, is gaining relevance in the first place. The self-development of an individual, the creative application of knowledge in certain situations, that is, the finding of one's own personality, the optimal way to solve various problems and problems (Cahapay, 2020). The development of the creative abilities of future educators-psychologists is one of the main tasks of higher professional education. The path to the success of an individual lies through a creative approach to work. At the same time, the creative approach is especially important in the profession of an educator-psychologist (Gonzalez, 2020). Advanced pedagogy sees the main task of teaching not in the simple transfer of a certain amount of ready-made knowledge to students, but in the development of their creative independent thinking.

The studies studied show that Luke (1973), a famous researcher of the problem of creativity, identifies the following creative abilities.

1. Ability to see the problem where others do not see it;
2. The ability to reduce mental operations, replace several concepts with one, and use signs that are increasingly wider in informational communication;
3. The ability to apply the skills acquired in solving one problem to solving another;
4. The ability to perceive reality as a whole without disassembling it into parts;
5. Ability to easily connect distant concepts; 6. The ability of memory to provide the necessary information at the right time;
7. The ability to choose one of the alternatives to solve the problem before testing;
8. The ability to enter newly acquired information into existing knowledge systems;
9. Ability to see things as they are;
10. Ideas are easy to create [6].

It will be appropriate for the student to master the following methods of creative thinking during the educational activities: - not an informant, the ability to study information without getting acquainted with it, but a problem in which something is clear even to others; - the ability to round mental processes. Because, in the process of student thinking, a person makes the transition from one stage in the sequence of thinking to another, so it is not always possible to cover the whole picture, the whole phenomenon, to reflect from the first step to the last. The process of rounding mental

processes is defined by the manifestation of the ability to replace several data with data associated with a high indicator of uncertainty.

- ability to apply in practice. It is associated with many phenomena and laws on the part of a person in practical and everyday activities. The skills acquired in solving one problem, as well as the ability to apply it to solving another problem on the basis of experiences, that is, the ability to distinguish the specific side of the problem from the uncharacteristic application to other areas in practice, are considered important. This is, in fact, the ability to develop a generalizing strategy. Additional is defined as the skill of finding new options or the necessary condition for the transfer of an idea.

The ability of one whole of perception. This means the ability to perceive information in one whole complex way. In this case, it is impossible to look at this problem from a new point of view, to see a new one for a long time.

For students, creative thinking skills are a concept that each teacher has a decisive role in the learning process. Giving students opportunities and space for creative thinking will certainly be effective in the long run. Creative activities, games and questions are endless. Consider trying to do one of these exercises at least once a week for your class, so that you will notice an improvement in activity as well as creativity. What is creative thinking in education? According to Campilis and Berki (2014), "creative thinking is thinking that allows students to apply their imagination in creating ideas, questions, and hypotheses, experimenting with alternatives, and evaluating their own and their peers' ideas, end products, and processes."

The importance of creative thinking for students the development of creative thinking in students has long been considered an important aspect of education and brain development. Harold Bloom (1956), an American literary scholar and teacher, devised Bloom's taxonomy of his study categories into 6 categories—creating the "final stage." Bloom argues that creation is an integral part of education in which students are allowed to produce their own unique work, explore solutions to problems, design a product, or develop a theory. Therefore, it can be said that creative thinking for students constitutes the peak of student knowledge and education.

Examples of creative thinking for students below are some methods, exercises, and activities that teachers and schools can use to develop students ' creative thinking skills in a group or even outside of class.

1) several games are recommended for creative thinking for students. For example," Dictionary story "this exercise can be very useful for teachers who like to increase students' interest in vocabulary and enrich their skills. So, get yourself a dictionary, choose a word at random and try to make a short story using the word you choose, the word above it, as well as the word below it. This exercise will open up your

students' chances of finding connections between words and mixing unrelated thoughts at a glance.

In the end, your students would have told stories from simple means. This can form the basis of your fiction writing classes and help your students stay true to ideas.

When six-word story teachers lose creative thinking exercises for students, they like to refer to an old-fashioned style called "six-word story". It primarily tests students' ability to be creative by using only six words to create a story.

Three elements make up a good six-word story: it makes sense for the student, takes him on a trip and leaves the student with emotion. A perfect example of this is "Hemingway's famous for sale: children's shoes. Never worn." Make sure you give this exercise to your students in the next lesson and watch their creative minds Bloom!

Avoid the letter 'E' French visual artist Henri Matisse said "Don't expect inspiration. It comes when working. "Recent research has disproved the myth that creativity is specific or genetic. On the contrary, scientists now believe that creativity is a skill that is achieved through regular training and exercise. An interesting way to develop your students' creative thinking skills is to play the game "avoid the letter e". This teaches their minds to be resourceful in the use of language.

B) creative thinking activities for students consider some of these creative thinking activities for students to use online or in a real classroom. - Look away from what you are creating the purpose of the exercise is to work on drawing what you actually see, rather than what you imagine. So basically you get a pen and a sheet of paper and give yourself 5 minutes. But don't look at the page while drawing. Instead, turn around and look at your hand while drawing, not the paper itself. The goal is to draw the details of your hand, not your entire hand. Also, avoid taking a pencil during this activity.

Focus on the amount each participant will be presented with 30 empty circles, a pencil and a sheet of paper in three minutes. The challenge is to fill as many circles as possible; the goal is quantity, not quality. Perhaps each of your circles will perceive the topic differently, or they are all emojis. Your only goal is to do as much as possible.

After the exercise, discuss and review any commonality you find and promote teamwork. In this game, if you are aiming for the amount, you do not have time to guess your plan a second time, because you can always change it later. At this time, the creative process develops. - Use a written request the subject of writing is entered and abbreviated through a written request. Writing guidelines are designed to arouse students' interest in the subject and inspire them to write critically and creatively about it.

An effective writing request should clearly define the writing task, in addition to entering and limiting the writing topic. Look at these instructions: what is something you always regret? What is something you have never told your parents? If you could only save one memory from your life, what would it be? Write about your spiritual life. First " describe."

C) creative thinking questions for students if you want to make your students think and engage at the beginning of the school year, asking creative thinking questions is a great way to meet new students and connect with the rest of the class as well. 15 creative thinking questions to inspire you. You will find questions that will answer elementary questions up to high school students!

Perhaps you can assign them to groups, couples or even individual students to make the activity richer: What is a machine that you can invent to make people's lives easier?

Draw or describe it. Can you make a list of 10 rhyming words? Let's use these words to write poetry. What if you were elected to open your own country? Discuss what makes a difference about it. If there is no electricity, How is the world we know different?

List ten different methods. What qualities would you use to explain the flower to someone you've never seen or heard of before? Can you write a story about a zoo without using any animal name? If tomorrow is a "day back", what will change in the world around us? How can people live like this? What would Five Ways life be different if we did not need sleep? How do you use this extra time? What would you choose if you could make one precious thing forever free?

Why did you choose this especially? If parents need to take a test before having a child, can you think of ten questions that will be on the test? Think of a way you can make \$100 next week. Do you really need teachers at school or can you just learn from the internet?

If you go back to the past and change something, what would it be and why? How would the world be different then? Name 10 different things you can do with a cup. What would you do if you were invisible one day? Where do you go? After all, as Albert Einstein once famously said, "Creativity is intelligence fun."

As a teacher based on the above, if you remind yourself every day that you are a big part of shaping their minds, you will never run out of ideas to stimulate creative thinking skills for students.

As a conclusion, it can be said that all the use of technologies aimed at developing students ' creativity gives them creative freshness that helps them develop creative thinking and other important skills. They are easily and freely available, and

teachers should easily accept them into their curriculum so that their students never lag behind when it comes to creativity, as this is very important for their comprehensive development. Share your thoughts, knowledge; helps to search for contextual explanations and additional knowledge.

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